

Development of a mutant strain of *Thiobacillus ferrooxidans* for removal of sulfur from coal

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Manuscript received 11 November 2011, revised 09 February 2012, accepted 14 March 2012

Abstract : Several *Thiobacillus ferrooxidans* isolated from sandy loamy soils are found to remove 12% of sulfur impurities from the Indian Coals (Jharia and Assam). Mutagenic agents, such as ethyl methane sulfonate (EMS) and UV-rays have been treated with a strain of *Thiobacillus ferrooxidans* in the present study. Out of one thousand two hundred isolates, each exhibited sulfur removal capacities of 25.0% on treatment with ethyl methane sulfonate. *Thiobacillus ferrooxidans* M₁ resulted higher value in comparison to the figure of the parent strain. On exposure to UV-rays, there are only four mutants of *Thiobacillus ferrooxidans* out of 875 isolates exhibited the highest sulfur removing capacities of 54.0%.

Keywords : *Thiobacillus ferrooxidans*, mutant strain, sulfur, coal.

Introduction

Almost all coals contain sulfur in varying quantities and its presence constitutes both metallurgical and environmental problems. It is accordingly desirable to reduce sulfur in coal to acceptable levels prior to coal utilization. The chemical desulfurization methods, however, have two major drawbacks, namely : (i) they are often expensive and (ii) they destroy the coking properties of coal. These factors have, by and large, militated against the adoption of these processes at the industrial scale although they may be suitable for social application¹⁻³.

In the past decade or so, studies have been made to re-examine the details of the removal of sulfur from coal by the accelerated microbial leaching process. The process is known to remove most of the pyritic sulfur as well as some of the organic sulfur in coal and does not affect the coking properties of coals. The process is also cheaper than chemical desulfurization. Two groups of microorganisms are involved in the removal of pyritic sulfur from coal. One group of microbes function at near room temperature while the other group is strictly thermophilic, i.e. they function at elevated temperatures. The microorganisms that are active at near room temperature comprise *Thiobacillus ferrooxidans* and other related thionic

bacteria⁴⁻⁹. The thermophiles comprise *Sulfolobus acidocaldarius*, *Sulfobacillus phermosulfidooxidans*, *Sulfolobus brierleji* and *Sulfolobus sultataricus*¹⁰⁻¹².

The possibility of desulfurization of coal by microbial leaching was first reported upto 23 to 27 wt. % of sulfur was leached from their coal samples after 30 days⁸. Recently, Dugan and Apel (1978) achieved almost total removal of pyrite sulfur from coal using a mixed culture of *Thiobacillus ferrooxidans* and *Thiobacillus thiooxidans*¹³. Silverman *et al.* (1963) investigated the effects of several physical factors on the dissolution rate of coal pyrite, sulfur ball and coarse crystalline pyrite using *Thiobacillus ferrooxidans* and *Thiobacillus thiooxidans* as oxidants¹⁴. *Thiobacillus thiooxidans* did not oxidize pyrite of any size⁹. The results also showed that particle size influenced rate of pyrite oxidation by *Thiobacillus ferrooxidans* the smaller the particle size, the faster the reaction¹¹. Detz and Barvinchak (1979) compared the desulfurization capabilities of the mesophilic *Thiobacillus ferrooxidans* and a mixed culture of the thermophilic microbes (*S. acidocaldarius* and *ferrolobus*)¹⁵. Stoner *et al.* (1990) have addressed the issue of enzyme accessibility related to removal of organic sulfur from coal¹⁶. These reviews lead to the conclusion that laboratory scale studies have

demonstrated the potential of biogenic sulfur removal from coal. The desulfurization of both as mine and refuse coal by microbes has been shown to be technically feasible. Although the process is still in its infancy, it appears to offer considerable technological potential for the treatment of coal fines and in the reclamation of coal from slurry ponds in the near future. So the microbial desulfurization technique described and proposed to be studied seems to have great potential and deserve attention.

A project for development of superior strains was undertaken in the laboratory with primary objective of improving the capacity of desulfurization of coal by strain selection. A strain of *Thiobacillus ferrooxidans* was treated with various mutagenic agents such as Ethyl Methane Sulfonate (EMS) and UV-rays and a series of experiments were conducted to investigate the problem.

Materials and methods :

Various samples of coal collected from Jharia and Assam sites were crushed in a ball mill to 200 mesh size for removal of sulfur.

Microorganisms : The pure culture of *Thiobacillus ferrooxidans* isolated from sandy loamy soils was used in this investigation. The *Thiobacillus ferrooxidans* is capable of removing 12% sulfur from coal where sulfur is present as the major impurity in the coal.

Mutagenic treatment : The parent culture used in the experiment was *Thiobacillus ferrooxidans* strain as selected out of sixty isolated of bacteria from various sources. Bacterial suspension was prepared in sterile normal saline water from the 7 days old bacterial liquid cultures. The preparation was thoroughly shaken and filtered twice through sterile cotton to remove bacterial clumps. The concentration of the bacterial suspension was finally made upto 10 cells/ml. The mutant strains were maintained on CM liquid medium having the following composition : $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$: 0.3%, KCl : 0.01%, KH_2PO_4 : 0.05%, $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$: 0.05%, $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$: 3%, pH : 2.0. It was sterilized at 14 °C for 15 min. 1% glucose was sterilized separately and was added to the medium aseptically. When the cultures were needed for mutational studies, they were transferred to CM liquid medium and incubated at 30 °C for 3 days with shaking device at 200 r.p.m. Cells were then washed with sterile normal saline water and the cell density was adjusted to 10^9 cells/ml.

This cell suspension was used both for mutational studies and for the inoculation of the fermentation medium. Submerged culture fermentation was carried out with the mutants.

Fermentation and analysis of coal samples : Total sulfur and different forms of sulfur contents of the coal samples were estimated according to the standard procedure¹². A coal slurry of 10% with acidified water (pH 2.0) was made. 50 ml of it was dispersed in 100 ml Erlenmeyer flasks. The flasks were then inoculated with 5 ml cell suspension (10^9 cells/ml) and incubated at 30 °C on a rotary shaker (200 r.p.m.). After definite periods, treated coal samples were filtered, washed with water, dried and analysed for total sulfur, pyritic sulfur and sulfate sulfur. The amount of organic sulfur was obtained by deducting the amount of pyritic and sulfate sulfur from total sulfur.

Treatment with EMS (Ethyl Methane Sulfonate) : Cells of *Thiobacillus ferrooxidans* from 72 h culture grown in CM medium were harvested and washed with the sterile distilled water and suspended in phosphate buffer (pH 7.6). The suspension containing 10^9 cells/ml was exposed to the action of EMS solution of different concentrations for a definite period. After the reaction, the mutagen (EMS) was inactivated by adding 6% sodium thiosulfate solution containing 0.05% Tween 80 and the cells were then washed 3–4 times with sterile distilled water. The cell suspension after proper dilution was then plated in CM agar for 72 h at 30 °C for determination of viable counts.

Treatment with UV-rays : 2 ml of cell suspension in sterile normal saline solution (containing 10^9 cells/ml) taken in a petridish (5 cm diameter) were exposed to UV-rays at a distance of 12 cm. The source of radiation was a Hanovia germicidal lamp (15 watt). The treated bacterial cells were then transferred to CM agar medium for 72 h at 30 °C for determination of viable counts.

Results and discussion

Effects of EMS concentration : The cell suspension of *Thiobacillus ferrooxidans* was exposed to 0.05 to 0.2 M EMS for 120 min. The scoring of survivors and productive variants is depicted in Fig. 1. Complete inactivation of cells took place at 0.2 M EMS in 120 min. The productive variants were detectable upon treatment with 0.05 M EMS and their number increased with increasing con-

Fig. 1. Percentage survival curve of *Thiobacillus ferrooxidans* and productive variants by treatment with different concentrations of EMS.

centration of EMS. A maximum of 80 productive variants were obtained at 0.02 M EMS.

Effects of period of treatment : Using 0.2 M EMS as a suitable concentration, the cells hours were treated with the mutagen for different period of time. The survivors and productive variants are plotted in Fig. 2, showing a lag in the inactivation of cells. After 60 min the death rate increased rapidly with time of exposure, giving a survival percentage of 0.5 in 180 min. The maximum number of productive (+) variants was scored at 120 min. In all 1200 isolates after treatment of EMS were tested for sulfur removing from coal.

Fig. 2. Percentage of *Thiobacillus ferrooxidans* variants by treatment with EMS for different periods of time.

Thiobacillus ferrooxidans M₁ gave higher sulfur removal capacity (25%) in fermentation medium. The parent strain of *Thiobacillus ferrooxidans* removed only 12% sulfur from coal.

Effect of UV-rays irradiation : The suspension (72 h) of *Thiobacillus ferrooxidans* M₁ obtained from EMS treatment was treated with UV-rays for different periods of time. The scoring of survivors and productive variants is depicted in Fig. 3. Complete inactivation of cells took place in 80 min. The productive variants were detectable upon treatment for 10 min and their number increased with increasing period of exposure. A maximum of 40 productive variants were obtained on exposure to UV-rays for 30 min. On exposure to UV-rays irradiation, there was only four mutants of *Thiobacillus ferrooxidans* out of 875 isolates exhibited the higher sulfur removing capacities of 54%.

Fig. 3. Percentage of *Thiobacillus ferrooxidans* variants obtained by exposure to UV-rays for different time intervals.

The present study shows that the mutagenic effects of EMS and UV-rays irradiation of *Thiobacillus ferrooxidans* are well distinguished from their lethal effects. EMS gives a survival curve in which a certain lag exists in the inactivation of cells during the initial stage. After 60 min, the death rate increases rapidly with time of exposure giving a survival percentage of 0.5% in 180 min. With UV-rays irradiation, there is a sharp killing effect (exponential curve). The total of 620 productive mutants were obtained and studied in the present work. It was observed that EMS treatment produced 30% productive variants including 10 (+) variants. UV-rays irradiation resulted in the fermentation of 40% productive variants which comprise 20% more productive (+) variants.

In the present study, we have observed the superiority of UV-rays irradiation for the development of high sulfur removing mutant of *Thiobacillus ferrooxidans*.

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